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USING TAX ADMINISTRATION INSTRUMENTS TO REDUCE THE TAX ON BUSINESS ENTITIES

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Abstract: This article examines the role of tax administration instruments in reducing the tax burden on business entities and improving the overall entrepreneurial environment. In modern economic conditions, the efficiency of tax administration is not limited to tax collection, but also includes simplifying tax procedures, reducing compliance costs, increasing transparency, and encouraging voluntary tax compliance. The study focuses on the importance of digital tax services, risk-based tax control, electronic reporting systems, tax incentives, and information exchange mechanisms between taxpayers and tax authorities. The article argues that the effective use of these instruments can reduce administrative pressure on businesses, improve the predictability of tax obligations, and create favorable conditions for sustainable business development. Special attention is given to the need for balancing fiscal interests of the state with the financial capacity of business entities. The findings suggest that improving tax administration mechanisms contributes not only to reducing the tax burden, but also to strengthening tax discipline, expanding the tax base, and increasing trust between the state and entrepreneurs.

Keywords: tax administration, tax burden, business entities, digital taxation, tax compliance, tax incentives, risk-based tax control, entrepreneurial environment, tax policy, electronic reporting.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada soliq ma'muriyatchiligi instrumentlarining tadbirkorlik subyektlari zimmasidagi soliq yukini kamaytirish va umumiy tadbirkorlik muhitini takomillashtirishdagi o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Zamonaviy iqtisodiy sharoitda soliq ma'muriyatchiligining samaradorligi faqat soliqlarni yig'ish bilan cheklanib qolmay, balki soliq tartib-taomillarini soddalashtirish, soliq majburiyatlarini bajarish bilan bog'liq xarajatlarni kamaytirish, shaffoflikni oshirish hamda ixtiyoriy soliq intizomini rag'batlantirishni ham o'z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqotda raqamli soliq xizmatlari, riskga asoslangan soliq nazorati, elektron hisobot tizimlari, soliq imtiyozlari hamda soliq to'lovchilar va soliq organlari o'rtasidagi axborot almashinuvi mexanizmlarining ahamiyatiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Maqolada ushbu instrumentlardan samarali foydalanish biznes subyektlariga nisbatan ma'muriy bosimni kamaytirishi, soliq majburiyatlarining prognoz qilinishini yaxshilashi hamda tadbirkorlik faoliyatining barqaror rivojlanishi uchun qulay sharoit yaratishi asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, davlatning fiskal manfaatlarini bilan tadbirkorlik subyektlarining moliyaviy imkoniyatlari o'rtasida muvozanatni ta'minlash zarurligi ta'kidlangan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, soliq ma'muriyatchiligi mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish nafaqat soliq yukini kamaytirishga, balki soliq intizomini mustahkamlashga, soliq bazasini kengaytirishga va davlat hamda tadbirkorlar o'rtasidagi ishonchni oshirishga ham xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: soliq ma'muriyatchiligi, soliq yuki, tadbirkorlik subyektlari, raqamli soliqqa tortish, soliq intizomi, soliq imtiyozlari, riskga asoslangan soliq nazorati, tadbirkorlik muhiti, soliq siyosati, elektron hisobot.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается роль инструментов налогового администрирования в снижении налоговой нагрузки на субъекты предпринимательства и совершенствовании общей предпринимательской среды. В современных экономических условиях эффективность налогового администрирования не ограничивается только сбором налогов, но также включает упрощение налоговых процедур, сокращение издержек соблюдения налоговых требований, повышение прозрачности и стимулирование добровольного соблюдения налогового законодательства. В исследовании особое внимание уделено значению цифровых налоговых услуг, риск-ориентированного налогового контроля, систем электронной отчетности, налоговых льгот и механизмов информационного обмена между налогоплательщиками и налоговыми органами. В статье обосновывается, что эффективное использование данных инструментов способствует снижению административного давления на бизнес, повышению предсказуемости налоговых обязательств и созданию благоприятных условий для устойчивого развития предпринимательства. Особое внимание уделяется необходимости обеспечения баланса между фискальными интересами государства и финансовыми возможностями субъектов предпринимательства. Результаты исследования показывают, что совершенствование механизмов налогового администрирования

способствует не только снижению налоговой нагрузки, но и укреплению налоговой дисциплины, расширению налоговой базы и повышению доверия между государством и предпринимателями.

Ключевые слова: налоговое администрирование, налоговая нагрузка, субъекты предпринимательства, цифровое налогообложение, соблюдение налоговых обязательств, налоговые льготы, риск-ориентированный налоговый контроль, предпринимательская среда, налоговая политика, электронная отчетность.

INTRODUCTION

In a market economy, the effective operation of business entities directly depends not only on the level of tax rates, but also on the simplicity, transparency and predictability of the process of fulfilling tax obligations. Therefore, tax administration is an important institutional element of the business environment. Practice shows that even a relatively moderate tax burden can create significant administrative costs for business activities if the process of submitting tax reports, preparing documents, passing inspections and communicating with tax authorities is complicated.

Although the main task of tax administration is to ensure stable revenues to the state budget, modern approaches interpret its role much more broadly. In particular, tax administration should serve to increase taxpayers' legal awareness, increase voluntary compliance, reduce tax disputes, bring economic activity into the formal sector, and strengthen trust between business and the state. Such an approach does not deny the control function of tax authorities, but rather requires its organization on a purposeful, fair, and analytical basis.

The quality of tax administration for business entities is reflected in several dimensions. First, the time and costs spent on fulfilling tax obligations should be as low as possible. Second, tax legislation and practical requirements should be understandable for the entrepreneur. Third, the criteria for control measures applied by tax authorities should be known in advance, consistent and transparent. Fourth, the taxpayer should be guaranteed the opportunity to correct errors, obtain explanations and appeal.

In Uzbekistan, in recent years, the modernization of the tax system, the expansion of electronic services, the strengthening of digital communication with taxpayers, and the reduction of administrative pressure on business have become urgent issues. Electronic invoices, online cash registers, personal accounts, automated reporting systems, and data exchange mechanisms are taking tax administration to a new level. However, if the external appearance of digitalization is not reinforced by its internal functional coherence, convenience for the entrepreneur will not be sufficiently formed.

The purpose of this article is to scientifically substantiate the priority areas for improving tax administration in the business environment. The study theoretically reveals the impact of tax administration on the business environment, analyzes modern approaches used in international experience, summarizes existing problems in the conditions of Uzbekistan, and develops proposals for the formation of a business-friendly, transparent, and effective tax administration model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Tax administration is increasingly recognized not only as a mechanism for revenue collection, but also as an important instrument for improving the business environment, reducing administrative tax burdens, and supporting sustainable economic growth. In recent years, international organizations and scholars have paid significant attention to the modernization of tax administration systems through digitalization, risk-based management, and simplified compliance procedures aimed at reducing costs for business entities.

Aslett, González, Hamilton, and Pecho (2024) emphasized the growing importance of analytical tools in modern tax administration systems. Their study highlighted that the use of compliance risk management, big data analytics, and digital monitoring technologies allows tax authorities to improve control efficiency while simultaneously reducing unnecessary administrative pressure on compliant taxpayers. The authors argued that risk-based tax administration systems contribute to lower compliance costs and reduce the time businesses spend dealing with tax procedures.

Begiashvili (2020) analyzed the main elements of improving tax administration and examined the impact of electronic services, transparency, and institutional efficiency on entrepreneurial activity. According to the author, simplifying administrative tax procedures increases voluntary tax compliance among business entities and contributes to reducing the shadow economy. The study also stressed the importance of strengthening communication and information exchange mechanisms between taxpayers and tax authorities.

Corbacho, Cibils, and Lora (2013) investigated the role of taxation and tax administration in economic development. The authors argued that effective tax administration creates a balance between the fiscal interests of the state and the financial capacity of businesses. Their research interpreted tax administration not only as a revenue collection mechanism, but also as a tool for improving the investment climate, supporting

entrepreneurship, and stimulating economic growth. The study further demonstrated that electronic filing systems, automated monitoring, and service-oriented tax administration significantly reduce administrative costs for firms.

Dabla-Norris, Misch, Cleary, and Khwaja (2017) provided empirical evidence on the relationship between tax administration and firm performance in emerging and developing economies. Their findings showed that complicated and inefficient tax administration negatively affects business productivity and investment activity. In contrast, transparent and digitalized tax systems reduce compliance costs and improve the operational efficiency of firms. The authors particularly emphasized that reducing administrative burdens for small and medium-sized enterprises plays an important role in encouraging business activity and improving economic performance.

The International Monetary Fund (2015) analyzed current challenges in revenue mobilization and improving tax compliance. The report highlighted that the introduction of user-friendly electronic tax services, integrated databases, and risk-based audit systems can substantially improve the effectiveness of tax administration. It was also noted that reducing the cost of tax compliance positively influences business development and increases voluntary compliance among taxpayers.

The OECD (2022) provided comparative information on tax administration systems in both advanced and emerging economies. The report demonstrated that countries with highly digitalized tax administration systems tend to achieve higher efficiency in tax collection while significantly reducing administrative costs for businesses. According to the OECD, electronic reporting systems, automated control mechanisms, and remote tax services are among the most important instruments for improving the business environment and enhancing the effectiveness of tax administration.

Overall, the reviewed literature demonstrates that modern tax administration instruments play a significant role not only in strengthening fiscal capacity, but also in reducing the administrative tax burden on business entities and creating a more favorable entrepreneurial environment. In particular, digitalization, risk-based control, electronic services, and integrated information systems are considered key directions for improving tax administration efficiency and supporting sustainable business development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research used the methods of scientific-abstract, systematic analysis, comparative analysis, institutional approach and logical generalization. Tax administration was studied as an institutional system inextricably linked with the business environment. In this case, the activities of tax authorities, taxpayer obligations, electronic services, control mechanisms, voluntary compliance and tax risk management were interpreted as an interconnected system.

The information base of the study was formed by scientific and practical sources published by the OECD, IMF, World Bank and international tax administration. These sources cover a wide range of issues such as digitalization of tax administration, management of compliance risks, reduction of taxpayer costs, improvement of service quality and optimization of audit selection. The study analyzed these approaches from the perspective of practical needs related to the business environment of Uzbekistan.

The analysis in the article was conducted mainly qualitatively. The impact of tax administration on the business environment was assessed based on the following criteria: ease of fulfilling tax obligations; degree of digitization of tax reports and payments; risk-based control and inspections; legal certainty for the taxpayer; quality of information exchange between tax authorities and entrepreneurs; opportunities to reduce tax disputes and administrative costs.

The comparative analysis examined elements such as service-oriented management, segmented taxpayer policies, early warning mechanisms, automated compliance checks, e-advisory services, and risk profiles, which are widely used in countries with developed tax administrations. These elements were assessed in relation to the characteristics of business entities' activities, information capabilities, and accounting capacity.

The institutional approach has made it possible to view tax administration as a system that regulates trust, commitment, and cooperation between the state and business. According to this approach, the tax authority is not only a regulatory entity, but also an institution that helps entrepreneurs form the right tax behavior, prevents errors in advance, and encourages legal activity.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the study show that the effectiveness of tax administration in the business environment depends on three main factors: first, the simplicity of the tax compliance process; second, the fairness and risk-based nature of the control system; and third, the service-oriented activities of tax authorities. These factors

are directly related to each other, and a problem in any of them creates additional costs, uncertainty and legal risks for business entities.

The first conclusion is that digitalization is central to improving tax administration. Digital tax services simplify the processes of reporting, making payments, issuing invoices, tracking tax debts, and communicating with tax authorities. However, digitalization should not be limited to simply converting existing complex processes into electronic form. It should ensure functional integration between business processes, banking information, accounting systems, and tax authorities' databases.

- tax control the transition to a risk- based model will significantly improve the business environment. In the traditional approach, almost the same control measures can be applied to all taxpayers. This creates an excessive administrative burden even for disciplined entrepreneurs. In the risk-based approach, tax authorities focus inspection resources on high-risk transactions, suspicious documents, inconsistent calculations, and activities with a high probability of tax evasion.

- tax administration as the service function increases, voluntary tax discipline increases. In order for an entrepreneur to properly fulfill his tax obligations, he must understand the legislation, quickly obtain the necessary information, conveniently use electronic services, and have the opportunity to correct errors before they are punished. Therefore, modern tax authorities must become not only a supervisory agency, but also an institution that advises, explains, and cooperates with taxpayers.

- electronic invoicing, online cash register techniques, and automated data exchange increase transparency in the business environment. Such systems provide near-real-time information on turnover, the value-added tax chain, and purchase and sale transactions. As a result, it is possible to reduce fraudulent transactions, identify cases of tax base evasion, and strengthen discipline in settlements between business entities.

- entrepreneurship in the environment for tax administration to be effective, it is necessary to move from a 'single control' model to a 'segmented approach' model. It is not effective to apply the same administrative requirements to large enterprises, small businesses, individual entrepreneurs, newly established entities and high-risk sectors. Each group has different tax risks, information capabilities, accounting capacity and administrative costs.

- tax administration entrepreneurship the impact on the environment is both direct and indirect. The direct impact is reflected in the costs of filing tax returns, making payments, undergoing inspections, and processing documents. The indirect impact is reflected in the investment decisions of entrepreneurs, their desire to expand their businesses, their motivation to work in the formal sector, and their trust in government institutions.

- tax administration the human factor is also important in improving the quality of tax administration. Digital systems help to identify complex situations, sort out risks and reduce errors. However, understanding the specifics of business activities, communicating with taxpayers, resolving disputes amicably and exercising professional judgment are determined by the qualifications of tax authorities. Therefore, technological modernization must be carried out in parallel with increasing human resources capacity.

Based on the results of the analysis, the main areas of tax administration impacting the business environment are summarized as follows (Table 1):

Table 1. Main Directions of Tax Administration Improvement and Their Impact on the Business Environment¹

Direction	Impact on the business environment	Expected result
Digitization	Reduces reporting, payment, and document management costs	Time savings and increased transparency
Risk-based control	Focuses investigations on high-risk cases	Reduction of unreasonable administrative pressure
Service approach	Strengthens taxpayer advice and explanation	Increased voluntary tax discipline
Segmented management	Provides a tailored approach to different business groups	Fair and flexible administration

The issue of improving tax administration in the business environment is not just a technical or organizational issue. It is, first of all, a question of institutional trust between the state and business. If an entrepreneur perceives the tax authority only as a punitive and inspecting body, then compliance with tax obligations often becomes mandatory. On the contrary, if the tax authorities operate in a transparent, predictable and consultative manner, a culture of voluntary compliance among entrepreneurs will be strengthened.

In the conditions of Uzbekistan, the digitalization of tax administration can bring significant positive

¹ Source: Author's own elaboration.

results. Electronic services and automated information exchange reduce time costs for businesses. However, digitalization alone is not enough. If electronic systems are complex, incomprehensible, or have frequent technical failures, they will become an additional burden for business entities, not a relief. Therefore, user experience, system stability, data protection, the convenience of personal accounts, and the possibility of two-way communication with the taxpayer are important in digitalization.

The development of risk-based control in tax administration is also relevant. A risk-based system protects entrepreneurs from unreasonable inspections and helps to effectively direct the resources of tax authorities. However, the risk criteria must be transparent, understandable and fair. An entrepreneur must know why he fell into a high-risk category, have the opportunity to correct mistakes and prove that he is a disciplined taxpayer. Otherwise, the risk system can become a source of uncertainty for business.

Another aspect of tax administration in the business environment important aspect - the quality of tax legislation explanations. Small businesses often have difficulty interpreting complex tax regulations on their own. This can lead to errors, fines, or excessive costs for informal consulting services. Therefore, tax authorities should develop simple-language guides, interactive calculators, video guides, industry-specific question-and-answer databases, and quick consultation channels.

Taxpayer incentives are also important in improving tax administration. For example, reducing the number of inspections for compliant entrepreneurs, expediting tax refunds, automatic recognition of overpayments, and early warning and advice mechanisms for tax arrears will increase voluntary compliance. This approach is based on the principle of prevention rather than punishment.

According to the scientific approach developed in the article, improving tax administration in the business environment in Uzbekistan should be carried out in several integral directions. First, it is necessary to gradually transition tax administration from a 'control-oriented model' to a 'service and compliance incentive model'. Second, it is necessary to expand risk-based analysis in tax control, but make risk criteria and results understandable for entrepreneurs. Third, it is necessary to form a single tax information space by integrating electronic invoices, online cash registers, bank data and customs information.

Fourth, simplified reporting, automatic reminders, advance error detection and self-correction mechanisms for small businesses should be introduced. Fifth, it is necessary to improve the skills of tax authorities in digital analytics, communication, understanding of business processes and professional ethics. Sixth, pre-trial resolution of tax disputes, appeal mechanisms and systems for protecting the rights of entrepreneurs should be strengthened.

Based on the results of the discussion, the final effect of improving tax administration should be assessed not only by increasing budget revenues, but also by the legalization of the activities of business entities, increased investment activity, reduction of the shadow economy, and strengthening business confidence in state institutions. In this sense, tax administration is not only an administrative tool of fiscal policy, but also an institutional factor of economic development.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving tax administration in the business environment is one of the important conditions for ensuring economic growth, budget stability and business activity. The results of the study showed that the effectiveness of tax administration is determined not by tax rates or the strictness of fiscal control, but by the simplicity, transparency, fairness and digital convenience of the tax compliance process.

Modern tax administration should not be focused on punishing entrepreneurs, but on facilitating their correct and timely fulfillment of tax obligations. To this end, the principles of a service approach, risk-based control, data analytics, digital services, taxpayer segmentation, and legal certainty should be a priority in the activities of tax authorities.

The most important areas for improving tax administration in Uzbekistan include improving the quality of electronic services, simplifying tax obligations for business entities, making the risk-based audit system more transparent, strengthening understandable advice and support mechanisms for small businesses, ensuring fair use of electronic invoicing and data exchange systems, and developing procedures for quick and impartial resolution of tax disputes.

In general, improving tax administration is a direct institutional tool for improving the business environment. Effective tax administration provides the state with stable revenues, and for entrepreneurs it provides legal certainty, reduced administrative burdens, and the opportunity to conduct competitive business. Therefore, tax administration reforms should always be carried out in harmony with the real needs of business entities, the capabilities of digital infrastructure, and the principles of fair supervision.

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